
**PERCEIVED EFFECTS OF COVID-19 LOCKDOWN ON THE FOOD
SECURITY STATUS OF VEGETABLE FARMERS IN IMO STATE**

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Abstract

The study accessed the perceived effects of COVID-19 lockdown on the food security status of vegetable farmers in Imo State, Nigeria. The study specifically ascertained their food security status before and amidst the COVID-19 lockdown; determined the output of fluted pumpkin before and amidst the COVID-19 lockdown; identified the perceived effect of COVID-19 lockdown on vegetable production and identified the measures farmers adopted to curtail the effect of COVID-19 on their food security. Multi-stage sampling procedure was used to select 100 vegetable farmers. Data were collected using questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics, the core food security module and paired sample t-test. The analysis of their food security status showed that the farmers were food insecure without hunger. The result of the t-test revealed that there was a significant difference between the output of fluted pumpkin farmers before the lockdown (2.425) and amidst the lockdown (1.985) at 1% significant level. Analysis of the measures adopted by the farmers in curtailing the effects of the COVID-19 lockdown on their food security include among others established a customer base in their locality (91%), diversified into other fields (79%), The study therefore concludes that the COVID-19 lockdown had an adverse effect on the food security of vegetable farmers in Imo State. The study recommended that government and non-governmental agencies should provide support and initiatives to small scale vegetable farmers affected by the lockdown.

Keywords: *COVID-19, food security, vegetable farmers and Imo State*